

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Cost Evaluation Report

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Executive summary

This report includes the cost Evaluation (Task 3.3) under the system Analysis (WP 3). This report mainly contains Four Chapters including; Cost evaluation of the sensors and other electronic equipment, Cost effectiveness of the 4nse system, Indirect cost for WS and Comparison of 4nse WS cost with other Automatic WS

Chapter 01 - Introduction

This chapter includes the cost evaluation of the sensors and other electronic equipment which purchased from Local and International Markets for install weather stations. Table 1 shows the sensors and other electronic equipment bought from the Local and International market.

Sensors/ Other Electronic Equipment	International Market	Local Market
Sensors		
6465 Davis Aero Cone Rain collector	√	
DS18B20 Temperature sensor	√	√
Anemometer 485 wind direction sensor	√	
ZHIPU wind Speed sensor	√	
SI1145 UV IR Visible Sensor Module	√	
BME280 sensor	√	√
HRXL-MaxSonar-WRLST water Level Sensor	√	
BH 1750 Light sensor Module		√
Soil Moisture Sensor Module		√
DHT 11 Sensor		√
Other Electronic Equipment		
OpenLog	√	
Arduino Mega 2560		√
Arduino UNO		√
DS3231 RTC		√
SIMCOM SIM800		√
SD Module		√
Relay Module		√
100W Solar chargers		√
30W Solar Panels		√
12V, 7Ah rechargeable battery		√
Step Down – LM2596 regulator		√
DC Step up voltage regulator		√
LM338K DC Voltage Regulator		√

Table 1: Cost evaluation of the Sensors and Equipment bought from the International & Local Market

1 Cost evaluation of the Sensors and Equipment bought from the International Market

The sensors and other equipment bought from the international market include Rain gauges, Temperature sensors, Wind Direction Sensors, Wind speed sensors, UVIR Visible sensor Module, BME 280, OpenLog and Water level Sensor.

Rain Gauges (6465 Davis Aero Cone Rain collector)

The standard instrument for the measurement of rainfall is the 203 mm (8 inch) rain gauge. In modern automatic weather stations a Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge (TBRG) is employed, which also has an aperture of 203 mm.

For measure the precipitation, 6465 Davis Aero Cone Rain collector was selected in the 4nse system. This pluviometer has a collector of 16.5 cm diameter and 24 cm high and the resolution is 0.2 mm. The accuracy is $\pm 4\%$ of total or 0.2mm up to 50 mm/h, $\pm 5\%$ of total or 0.2mm up to 100 mm/h whichever is greater. The range is from 0.0 to 999.8 mm/day.

Unit price for this Rain gauge in February 2017 was USD 76.95. It was increased up to USD 88 in end of the year 2017. Figure 1 shows the cost evaluation of the Rain Gauge. The average unit cost of this rain gauge was USD 84.66.

Figure 1: Cost Evaluation of Rain Gauge

Table 2 shows the Purchasing History of the Rain Guage such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. In 2017 to 2018 period, it was purchased total quantity of 41 Rain Gauges. The total quantity price was USD 3,494.91 and shipping cost was USD 2,541.48. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 6,036.39 for purchases the Rain Guages. (*consider the shipping cost of USD 1,780.00 include 26 Rain collectors, 03 Vantage pro2 and 03 USB purchased from Davis Instrument corporation)

Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Remarks	Seller
2/3/2017	1	76.95	76.95	34.33	111.28		Sparkfun
8/25/2017	4	84.99	339.96	168.80	508.76		ebay - Dotpins
11/20/2017	2	88.00	176.00	135.00	311.00		Beijing GuoxInhuayaan Technology
2/8/2018	4	88.00	352.00	249.09	601.09		Beijing GuoxInhuayaan Technology
4/24/2018	4	85.00	340.00	174.26	514.26		ebay - Dotpins
6/25/2018	26	85.00	2,210.00	1,780.00*	3,990.00	shipping cost include 26 Rain collector, 03 Vantage pro2 and 03 USB purchased from Davis Instrument corporation	Davis
Total	41	507.94	3,494.91	2,541.48	6,036.39		

Table 2: Purchasing History of Rain Gauge

Temperature sensors

Considering the costs and accuracies of the different technologies we have selected the DS18B20 and the DHT22 as possible candidate, in particular the DS18B20 due to its waterproof characteristics is well suited for external positioning. More information about this sensor is given in 4nse D2.1 System Design Report.

Within the year 2017, it was decreased USD 0.11 for the unit cost of this Temperature sensor. The unit price of this sensor in November 2017 was USD 2.20 and December 2017 was USD 2.09. Figure 2 shows the cost evaluation of this sensor.

Figure 2: Cost Evaluation of Temperature Sensor

Table 3 shows the Purchasing History of the DS18B20 Temperature sensor such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. The total quantity of DS18B20 Temperature sensor was 10. And the total quantity price was USD 4.29 and shipping cost was USD 13.38. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 34.83 for purchases the DS18B20 Temperature sensor.

Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Seller
11/18/2017	5	2.20	11.00	6.69	17.69	Ali Express
12/8/2017	5	2.09	10.45	6.69	17.14	Ali Express
Total	10	4.29	21.45	13.38	34.83	

Table 3: Purchasing History of the DS18B20 Temperature sensor

Wind Direction sensors

For measure the Wind Direction, Anemometer 485 wind direction sensor is selected in the 4nse system compared prior to the SEN-08942 sensor. Compared to SEN-08942, Anemometer 485 has better accuracy and durability. More information about this sensor is given in 4nse D2.2 System Prototype Report.

In the beginning of the project, it developed only PCB type Weather station. But after the development of MOD type weather station, it was decided to used two type of Anemometers for PCB and MOD station.

For PCB Type Weather Station, the unit cost of wind direction sensor was USD 52 from 2017 to 2019 time period. For MOD type Weather Station unit cost of wind direction sensor was USD 14.10 in 2018 and it was decreased by USD 0.34 in 2019. Figure 3 shows the cost evaluation of these sensors.

Figure 3: Cost Evaluation of Wind Direction Sensor

Table 4 shows the Purchasing history of the Wind Direction sensors (PCB and MOD) such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. It seems PCB unit cost is much higher than MOD unit cost. In 2017 to 2019 period, we purchased total quantity of 20 Wind Direction - PCB sensors and 19 Wind Direction – MOD sensors. And the total quantity price was USD 1,040.00 for the Wind Direction - PCB sensors including free shipping. The total quantity price was USD 266.54 and shipping cost was USD 439.18 for the Wind Direction - MOD sensors. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 1,040.00 for purchases the Wind Direction - PCB sensors and the total expenditure was USD 705.72 for purchases the Wind Direction – MOD sensors . Therefore the total expenditure cost for purchasing both PCB and MOD Wind Direction sensors was USD 1,745.72.

Wind Direction sensor - PCB							
Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Seller	
8/25/2017	4	51.15	204.60	181.53	386.13	Ali Express	
11/18/2017	1	52.00	52.00	Free	52.00	Ali Express	
12/8/2017	1	52.00	52.00	Free	52.00	Ali Express	
2/22/2018	3	52.00	156.00	Free	156.00	Ali Express	
6/28/2018	2	52.00	104.00	Free	104.00	Ali Express	
1/22/2019	4	52.00	208.00	Free	208.00	Ali Express	
1/27/2019	9	52.00	468.00	Free	468.00	Ali Express	
Total	24	363.15	1,244.60	181.53	1,426.13		
Wind Direction sensor - MOD							
Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Seller	
1/23/2018	8	14.10	112.80	222.43	335.23	Ali Express	
1/31/2018	7	14.10	98.70	199.63	298.33	Ali Express	
1/12/2019	4	13.76	55.04	17.12	72.16	Ali Express	
Total	19	41.96	266.54	439.18	705.72		

Table 4: Purchasing History of the Wind Direction sensors

Wind Speed sensors

ZHIPU and SEN-08942 sensors were compared prior to the selection of ZHIPU sensor to measure the wind speed in the 4nse system. Compared to the SEN-08942, ZHIPU sensor has better accuracy and resolution. Further ZHIPU wind speed sensor is ideal for tropical country like Sri Lanka due to the following features:

- The sensor is made up of Alluminium Alloy material. Hence it is high in strength
- Weather resistance
- Anti corrosion
- Water resistance

More information about this sensor is given in 4nse D2.2 System Prototype Report. (Strigaro et al., 2017) In the beginning of the project, it developed only PCB type Weather station. But after the development of MOD type weather station, it was decided to used two type of Wind Speed sensors for PCB and MOD station.

For PCB Type Weather Station, the unit cost of the wind Speed sensor was USD 37.50 from 2017 to 2019 time period. In 2018 it was decreased up to USD 36.75. For MOD type Weather Station unit cost of the wind speed sensor was USD 8.45 in January 2018 and it was decreased up to USD 19.07 in May 2018. However, in January 2019, the unit cost is USD 13.76. Figure 4 shows the cost evaluation of these sensors.

Figure 4: Cost Evaluation of Wind Speed Sensor

Table 5 shows the Purchasing History of the Wind Speed sensors (PCB and MOD) such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. It seems PCB unit cost is much higher than MOD unit cost. In 2017 to 2019 period, we purchased total quantity of 21 Wind Speed - PCB sensors and 19 Wind Speed – MOD sensors. And the total quantity price was USD 777.75 and shipping cost was USD 64.08 for the Wind Speed - PCB sensors (Most of the transactions including free shipping) . The total quantity price was USD 229.63 and shipping cost was USD 251.17 for the Wind Speed - MOD sensors. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 841.83 for purchases the Wind Speed - PCB sensors and the total expenditure was USD 480.80 for purchases the Wind Speed – MOD sensors . Therefore the total expenditure cost for purchasing both PCB and MOD Wind Speed sensors was USD 1,322.63.

Wind Speed sensor - PCB								
Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)			Seller
11/18/2017	2	37.50	75.00	free	75.00			Ali Express
12/8/2017	2	37.50	75.00	free	75.00			Ali Express
2/22/2018	4	36.75	147.00	free	147.00			Ali Express
5/24/2018	6	36.75	220.50	free	220.50			Ali Express
5/25/2018	2	37.50	75.00	free	75.00			Ali Express
8/4/2018	3	36.75	110.25	free	110.25			Ali Express
1/12/2019	2	37.50	75.00	64.08	139.08			Ali Express
Total								
	21	260.25	777.75	64.08	841.83			
Wind Speed sensor - MOD								
Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)			Seller
1/31/2018	8	8.45	67.60	158.00	225.60			E bay
2/21/2018	4	9.79	39.16	78.37	117.53			E bay
5/23/2018	5	19.07	95.35	free	95.35			Ali Express
1/12/2019	2	13.76	27.52	14.80	42.32			Ali Express
Total								
	19	51.07	229.63	251.17	480.80			

Table 5: Purchasing History of the Wind Speed sensors

SI1145 UV IR Visible Sensor Module

In the beginning of the Project, the 4nse system used BH1750FVI sensor to measure the light intensity. The maximum capacity of this sensor is measure the light intensity up to 65klx. But normally we experienced >100klx light intensity in Sri Lanka. With this limitation, it was decided to used SI1145 UV IR Visible Sensor Module for measure the Light Intensity which having maximum capacity of 128klx. Figure 5 shows the cost evaluation of SI1145 UV IR Visible Sensor module.

The unit cost of this sensor was USD 5.12 from 2018. In 2019 it was decreased up to USD 3.74.

Figure 5: Cost Evaluation of Light Sensor Module

Table 6 shows the detailed description of the SI1145 UV IR Visible sensors such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. In 2018 to 2019 period, we purchased total quantity of 49 SI1145 UV IR sensors from International Market. And the total quantity price was USD 236.90 and shipping cost was USD 47.16. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 284.06 for purchases the SI1145 UV IR sensors.

Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Seller
2/21/2018	21	5.12	107.52	44.00	151.52	Ebay
5/25/2018	10	5.11	51.10	Free	51.10	Ebay
5/26/2018	5	5.11	25.55	Free	25.55	Ebay
6/26/2018	3	5.11	15.33	Free	15.33	Ebay
1/12/2019	10	3.74	37.40	3.16	40.56	Ali Express
Total	49	24.19	236.90	47.16	284.06	

Table 6: Purchasing History of the SI1145 UV IR Visible sensor

BME 280

HR202, DHT11, DHT22 and BME280 sensors were compared prior to the selection of BME280 sensor to measure the humidity. MPL3115A2, BMP280, MD-PS002 and BME280 sensors were compared prior to the selection of BME280 sensor to measure the atmospheric pressure.(Cannata et al., 2017) It was decided to use BME280 sensor for the 4nse system, since it comes with both pressure and humidity measuring capabilities.

The unit cost of this sensor was USD 18.95 in May 2018. And it cost decreased up to USD 9.95 in June 2018. Figure 6 shows the cost evaluation of this sensor.

Figure 6: Cost Evaluation of BME 280

Table 7 shows the detailed description of the BME 280 sensors such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. The most frequently replaced sensor is BME280, due to the corrosion problem. In the period of 2018 to 2019, we purchased a total quantity of 87 BME 280 sensors from International Market. And the total quantity price was USD 671.65 and shipping cost was USD 112.51. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 784.26 for purchases of the BME 280 sensors.

Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Seller
5/24/2018	15	18.95	284.25	30.90	315.15	Sparkfun
5/30/2018	6	19.95	119.70	31.03	150.73	Sparkfun
6/25/2018	16	9.95	159.20	30.82	190.02	Sparkfun
3/7/2019	50	2.17	108.50	19.76	128.26	Ali Express
Total	87	51.02	671.65	112.51	784.16	

Table 7: Purchasing History of the BME 280 sensors

Open Log

For keep track of the sensor data of the SD card, OpenLog – Data Logger is selected in the 4nse system. The unit cost of OpenLog was USD 14.20 in 2018 and it was increased up to USD 15.50 in 2019. Figure 7 shows the cost evaluation of this OpenLog.

Figure 7: Cost Evaluation of Open Log

Table 8 shows the detailed description of the OpenLog Data Logger such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. In 2018 to 2019 period, we purchased total quantity of 33 OpenLogs from International Market. And the total quantity price was USD 479.90 and

shipping cost was USD 64.35. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 544.25 for purchases the OpenLog Data Loggers.

Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Seller
1/23/2018	15	14.20	213.00	29.72	242.72	Sparkfun
5/30/2018	5	14.95	74.75	31.03	105.78	Sparkfun
6/25/2018	3	14.95	44.85	Free	44.85	Sparkfun
3/22/2019	10	14.73	147.30	3.60	150.90	Sparkfun
Total	33	58.83	479.90	64.35	544.25	

Table 8: Purchasing History of the OpenLog

HRXL-MaxSonar – WRLST Water Level Sensor

The River Gauge is comprised HRXL-MaxSonar – WRLST Water Level Sensor, Arduino Mega controller, Solar Panel of 30 W, 12V,35Ah sealed type battery and Reset Circuit.

HRXL-MaxSonar – WRLST Water Level Sensor is selected for 4ONSE River Gauge system to measure the Water Level. The unit cost of this sensor was USD 174.90.

Figure 8: Cost Evaluation of Water Level Sensor

Table 9 shows the Purchasing History of the Cost Evaluation of HRXL-MaxSonar-WRLST Water Level Sensor such as Quantity, Unit cost, shipping cost and sellers etc. We purchased total quantity of 07 HRXL-MaxSonar-WRLST Water Level Sensor from International Market within the two transactions. And the total quantity price was USD 1,224.30 and shipping cost was USD 134.97. Therefore the total expenditure was USD 1,359.27 for purchases this HRXL-MaxSonar-WRLST Water Level Sensor

Date of Purchased	Quantity	Unit Price (USD)	Total Price (USD)	Shipping Cost (USD)	Grand Total (USD)	Seller
8/13/2018	3	174.90	524.70	57.84	582.54	Maxbotix
8/14/2018	4	174.90	699.60	77.13	776.73	Maxbotix
Total	7	349.80	1,224.30	134.97	1,359.27	

Table 9: Purchasing History of the HC-SR 04 Ultrasonic water level sensor.

2 Cost evaluation of the Sensors and Equipment bought from the Local Market

The sensors and other equipment bought from the local market include Temperature sensors, BME 280, BH1750 Light Sensor Module, Soil Moisture Sensor Module, Arduino Mega 2560, Arduino UNO, DHT 11, DS3231 RTC, SIMCOM SIM800, SD Module, Relay Module, Solar Charger, Solar Panel, Battery, Step down – LM2596, DC Stepup Voltage Regulator and LM 338K DC Voltage Regulator.

The sensors and other Equipment brought from Local Market, recorded currency as LKR (Sri Lanka Rupees). For convert LKR values to USD, used the Exchange rate in particular purchasing dates. (Source: <https://www1.oanda.com>)

Temperature sensors – DS18B20

Considering the costs and accuracies of the different technologies we have selected the DS18B20 and the DHT22 as possible candidate, in particular the DS18B20 due to its waterproof characteristics is well suited for external positioning. More information about this sensor is given in 4nse D2.1 System Design Report.

In 2018, the unit cost of the sensor was increased from USD 1.36 to USD 1.73 (LKR 210.00 to LKR 280.00) in the local market. Figure 9 shows the cost evaluation of this sensor.

Figure 9: Cost Evaluation of DS18B20 Temperature Sensor

BME 280

HR202, DHT11, DHT22 and BME280 sensors were compared prior to the selection of BME280 sensor to measure the humidity. MPL3115A2, BMP280, MD-PS002 and BME280 sensors were compared prior to the selection of BME280 sensor to measure the atmospheric pressure (Cannata et al., 2017). It was decided to use BME280 sensor for the 4nse system, since it comes with both pressure and humidity measuring capabilities.

Figure 10: Cost Evaluation of BME 280

In the period of 2017 to 2019, the unit cost of this sensor was varied from USD 6.06 to USD 11.00 (LKR 950.00 to LKR 1,950.00).

Soil Moisture Sensor Module

During the designing stage of the weather station, a commercially available low cost soil moisture sensor was used. However, it was getting corroded with the time and consequently the resultant readings were received with an incremental error. Therefore, a new type of soil moisture was designed using stainless steel tubes which does not have any corrosion problem.

The unit cost of this sensor was increased from USD 0.64 to USD 1.38 (LKR 110.00 to LKR 220.00) in August 2017 to August 2018.

Figure 11: Cost Evaluation of Soil Moisture Sensor Module

Arduino Mega 2560

Arduino Mega 2560 is the Main Controller of the 4nse system. The unit cost of this item was varied from USD 9.11 to USD 12.27 (LKR 1,590.00 to 1,950.00) within 2018.

Figure 12: Cost Evaluation of Arduino Mega 2560

DHT 11

DHT 11 sensor selected to measure the system's internal temperature. The unit cost of this sensor is varied from USD 1.21 to USD 1.65 (LKR 190.00 to LKR 265.00) in 2018. Figure 13 shows the cost evaluation of this sensor.

Figure 13: Cost Evaluation of DHT 11

DS3231 RTC

DS3231 RTC is selected for 4nse main controlling and processing unit to set the timestamp for measuring data. The unit cost of this Module was varied from USD 1.33 to USD 2.16 (LKR 235.00- 380.00) in 2018. Figure 14 shows the cost evaluation of this Module.

Figure 14: Cost Evaluation of DS3231 RTC

SIMCOM SIM800

SIMCOM SIM800 is the GSM Module for data communication in 4nse main system block. The unit cost of this module was varied from USD 7.74 to USD 31.50 (LKR 1,200.00 to LKR 4,700.00) in 2017 to 2019 period. Figure 15 shows the cost evaluation of this module.

Figure 15: Cost Evaluation of SIMCOM SIM800

SD Module

SD Module in 4nse PCB main system block is used for data storage purposes. This module unit cost was increased from USD 0.59 to USD 1.12 (LKR 90.00 to LKR 180.00) within 2018. Figure 16 shows the cost evaluation of this module.

Figure 16: Cost Evaluation of SD Module

Relay Module

Relay Module is used to control the internal fan of the 4nse main system block. The unit cost of this module was varied from USD 0.65 to USD 3.85 (LKR 135.00 to LKR 620.00)

Figure 17: Cost Evaluation of Relay Module

Solar Charger

100W solar chargers are selected for the 4nse Main Station and River Guage to convert the solar energy to voltage and charge the Battery. The unit cost of this charger was varied from USD 9.38 to USD 18.12 (LKR1, 700.00 to LKR 2,850.00) in the purchasing period.

Figure 18: Cost Evaluation of Solar Charger

Solar Panel

30W Solar Panels selected for the 4nse system power supply section to controls solar panel voltage and the charging voltage to the battery. The unit cost of the sensor was varied from USD 21.61 to USD 41.54 (LKR 3,400.00 to LKR 7,300.00).

Figure 19: Cost Evaluation of Solar Panels

Battery

12V, 7Ah rechargeable battery used for stores solar energy and provides power to the system. The unit cost of this battery was varied from USD 7.79 to USD 60.69 (LKR 1,150.00 to LKR 9,290.00). Figure 20 shows the cost evaluation of this battery.

Figure 20: Cost Evaluation of Battery

Step Down – LM2596

LM2596 regulator is selected for the 4nse power system to regulate the +12V DC unregulated supply voltage to +9V DC voltage. The unit cost of this step down was varied from USD 0.74 to USD 3.01 (LKR 130.00 to LKR 475.00) in the purchasing period.

Figure 21: Cost Evaluation of LM 2596 Step Down

3 Cost Comparison of Sensors purchased from Local vs International Market

There are 02 sensors; *DS18B20 Temperature sensor* and *BME 280* brought from both local and international markets with considering the availability of the particular period and low cost. Below figures shows the cost comparison of these sensors evaluating both local and international market.

DS18B20 Temperature sensor

In 2017, Temperature sensors purchased from the international market and the unit cost of this sensor was USD 2.09 – USD 2.20 excluding shipping cost. For this transaction; shipping cost was USD 6.69. The total cost of this sensors was USD 17.14 - USD 17.69. In 2016 this sensor is available in local market but the unit price is much higher (USD 1.97). In 2018 this sensor was available as low cost (USD 1.24 -USD 1.65). Due to the comparison of unit cost in the international market vs Local market, it was decided to purchase Temperature sensors from local market considering the low cost. Figure 22 shows the cost comparison of the Temperature sensor.

Figure 22: Cost comparison of DS18B20 Temperature sensor

BME 280

Approximately, the Unit cost of the BME 280 was USD 8.51 per unit at Local market. Sometimes this BME 280 is not available in the local market and then it was purchased from

the International market. Approximately it cost USD 12.76 per unit in the international market, deliver with free shipping.

Figure 23: Cost comparison of BME 280

Chapter 02 - Introduction

This chapter includes the costs incurred in developing the two 4nse prototypes system with a river gauge. The costs have been separately calculated for components of the 4nse-mod system, 4nse-pcb system and 4nse river gauge. Also this Chapter Include the Shipping cost of each Items which purchased from the International Market and Cost incurred in developing the total 37 4nse Station including 16 MOD, 15 PCB and 06 River gauges.

1 Cost effectiveness of the 4nse-MOD system

Table 10 lists the cost incurred in developing the 4nse-MOD system including main station, main system block, power supply section and sensor unit, mounting and housing items. (Please consider Item cost and Shipping cost is calculated using Average cost)

No	Item	Description	Qty	Shipping Cost (USD)	Cost (USD)
components of the 4nse-MOD system block					
1	Arduino Mega2560	Main controller	1		11.47
2	DROK Module SIM800	GSM Module for data communication	1		9.12
3	OpenLog*	SD module for Data storage	1	1.95	14.71
4	RTC DS3231	To set the Time stamp for measured data	1		1.88
5	DHT 11	To measure the system's	1		

		internal temperature			1.24
7	LM 2596 Step-down convertor	To convert the voltage as Arduino and the other components requirement	2		1.65
Components of the solar power supply of the 4nse-MOD solution					
8	Reset Circuit	To reset the Circuit system	1		9.88
9	Solar Charger (12V,10Ah)	To charge the battery	1		20.00
10	Solar Panel (30W)	To charge the battery	1		28.82
11	Rechargeable battery (12V, 35Ah)	To power up the system	1		37.06
12	LM 7805 Voltage Regulator	To regulate the power	1		1.41
Sensors of the 4nse-MOD weather station					
13	DS18B20 Temperature Sensor	To measure the Temperature	1		1.76
14	UV IR Visible Light Sensor*	To measure the Light Intensity	1	0.96	4.84
15	YL-69 Soil Moisture Module	To measure the Soil Moisture	1		1.41
16	BME 280*	To measure atmospheric pressure and Humidity	1	1.29	12.76
17	Wind speed sensor*	To measure the wind speed	1	13.22	12.58
18	Wind Direction sensor*	To measure the wind Direction	1	23.11	13.99
19	6465 Davis Aerocone Rain Gauge with Mountable Base*	To measure the rainfall	1	62.00	84.99
components required for mounting and housing the main weather station					
20	Large size plastic box and Metal Box	(300x200x300 PVC/ 400*300*200) - To carry the main processing unit	2		70.59
21	Pole		1		126.47
22	concrete Works				17.65
23	Base				14.71
24	Miscellaneous**				135.70
Cost of the 4nse-MOD station (USD)				102.53	634.69
Total cost of the 4nse-MOD station (USD)					737.22
Total cost of the 4nse-MOD station (LKR)					125,327.40

Table 10: Cost of items of the 4nse-MOD system

Sensors were purchased from both local and international market. Hense, shipping charges were added for the sensors which purchased from the international market. They are marked in asterix mark (*).

*(Miscellaneous Items**- Resistors, Wires, Nut & Bolt, Stainless steel rod used in Soil Sensor, Stainless steel tube used for Light & BME sensors, Battery bracket & plate, Connectoe bars, Perspex sheet, Laser Cutting, SIM card, SD card, Spacers, Greese, BME & Light cup, cable tie, Headers, Rain Guage Plate etc.)*

2 Cost effectiveness of the 4nse-PCB system

Table 11 lists the cost incurred in developing the 4nse-PCB system including main station, main system block, power supply section and sensor unit, mounting and housing items. (Please consider Item cost and Shipping cost is calculated using Average cost) Sensors were purchased from both local and international market. Hense, shipping charges were added for the sensors which purchased from the international market. They are marked in asterix mark (*).

No	Item	Description	Qty	Shipping Cost (USD)	Cost (USD)
components of the 4onse-PCB system block					
1	Arduino Mega2560	Main controller	1		11.47
2	SIMCOM SIM800	GSM Module for data communication	1		9.12
3	SD Module	SD module for Data storage	1		1.12
4	RTC module with EEPROM	To set the Time stamp for measured data	1		1.88
5	16 x 2 Alphanumeric LCD	To display the data in the system	1		1.94
6	DHT 11	To measure the system's internal temperature	1		1.24
7	12V DC brushless Fan	For cooling the system	1		1.70
8	Relay Module (12V, 5A)	To control the internal fan of the system	1		1.65
9	LM 2596 Step-down convertor	To convert the voltage as Arduino and the other components requirement	2		1.65
10	DC Step-up Voltage Regulator	To boost the voltage in Wind Direction and Wind Speed Sensors.			2.06
11	Printed Circuit Board (PCB)	To connect all the components of the weather station	1		17.80
Components of the solar power supply of the 4onse-PCB solution					
12	Reset Circuit	To reset the Circuit system	1		9.88
13	Solar Charger (12V,10Ah)	To charge the battery	1		20.00
14	Solar Panel (30W)	To charge the battery	1		28.82
15	Rechargeable battery (12V, 35Ah)	To power up the system	1		37.06
16	LM 7805 Voltage Regulator	To regulate the power	1		1.41
Sensors of the 4onse-PCB weather station					
17	DS18B20 Temperature Sensor	To measure the Temperature	1		1.76
18	UV IR Visible Light Sensor*	To measure the Light Intensity	1	0.96	4.84
19	YL-69 Soil Moisture Module	To measure the Soil Moisture	1		1.41
20	BME 280*	To measure atmospheric pressure and Humidity	1	1.29	12.76
21	Wind speed sensor*	To measure the wind speed	1	3.05	37.50
22	Wind Direction sensor*	To measure the wind Direction	1	7.56	52.00
23	6465 Davis Aerocone Rain Gauge with Mountable Base*	To measure the rainfall	1	62	84.99
components required for mounting and housing the main weather station					
24	Large size Metal box	Metal Box (400*300*200)	1		35.29
25	Mounting Pole	3m height and 25mm diameter - To carry the boxes with components of the main weather station	1		126.47
26	Concrete Works				17.65
27	Base				14.71
28	Miscellaneous**				153.33
Other Costs					
Cost of the 4onse-PCB station (USD)				74.86	691.51
Total cost of the 4onse-PCB station (USD)					766.37
Total cost of the 4onse-PCB station (LKR)					130,282.90

Table 11: Cost of items of the 4onse-PCB system

(Miscellaneous Items**- Resistors, Capacitors, Transistors, IC, Heat Sink, Wires, Nut & Bolt, Stainless steel rod used in Soil Sensor, Stainless steel tube used for Light & BME sensors, Battery bracket & plate,, Perspex sheet, Laser Cutting, SIM card, SD card, Rain Gauge Plate, Buzzer, Spacers, Grease, BME & Light cup, cable tie, Headers, Soldering Iron, Flexible Hose, I2C etc.)

3 Cost effectiveness of the 4nse-PCB River Gauge system

Table 12 lists the cost incurred in developing the 4nse-PCB River gauge system including main system block, power supply section and sensor unit, mounting and housing items. (Please consider Item cost and Shipping cost is calculated using Average cost) Sensors were purchased from both local and international market. Hence, shipping charges were added for the sensors which purchased from the international market. They are marked in asterisk mark (*).

No	Item	Description	Qty	Shipping Cost (USD)	Cost (USD)
components of the 4nse-River Gauge					
1	Arduino Mega2560	Main controller	1		11.47
2	SIMCOM SIM800	GSM Module for data communication	1		9.12
3	SD Module	SD module for Data storage	1		1.12
4	RTC module with EEPROM	To set the Time stamp for measured data	1		1.88
5	16 x 2 Alphanumeric LCD	To display the data in the system	1		1.94
6	DHT 11	To measure the system's internal temperature	1		1.24
8	Relay Module (12V, 5A)	To control the internal fan of the system	1		1.65
9	LM 2596 Step-down convertor	To convert the voltage as Arduino and the other components requirement	2		1.65
11	Printed Circuit Board (PCB)	To connect all the components of the weather station	1		17.80
Components of the solar power supply of the 4nse-River Gauge					
12	Reset Circuit	To reset the Circuit system	1		9.88
13	Solar Charger (12V,10Ah)	To charge the battery	1		20.00
14	Solar Panel (30W)	To charge the battery	1		28.82
15	Rechargeable battery (12V, 35Ah)	To power up the system	1		37.06
Sensors of the 4nse-River Gauge					
17	HRXL - MaxSonar - WRLST*	To measure the Water Level	1	19.28	174.95
components required for mounting and housing the main weather station					
24	Large size Metal box	Metal Box (400*400*200)			35.29
25	Mounting Pole	3m height and 25mm diameter - To carry the boxes with components of the weather station			126.47
26	Concrete Works				17.65
27	Base				14.71
28	Miscellaneous				120.18
Cost of the 4nse-River Gauge (USD)				19.28	632.88
Total cost of the 4nse-River Gauge (USD)					652.16
Total cost of the 4nse-River Gauge (LKR)					110,867.98

Table 12: Cost effectiveness of the 4nse-PCB River Gauge system

(Miscellaneous Items**- Resistors, Capacitors, Transistors, IC, Heat Sink, Wires, Nut & Bolt, Lead, Sleeving, Battery bracket & plate,, Perspex sheet, Laser Cutting, SIM card, SD card, Reset Switch, Buzzer, Terminals, Spacers, Grease, cable tie, Headers, Soldering Iron, I2C etc.)

According to the above Tables, the total approximate cost for building the 4nse - MOD station is about USD 737.22 including USD 102.53 for shipping charges for some sensors. The cost for building the 4nse - PCB station is about USD 766.37 including USD 74.86 for shipping charges. And the cost for building the 4nse – River Gauge is about USD 652.16.

4 Shipping Cost of the Sensors

Table 13 shows the Summary of total shipping cost for Items which purchased from the International market. Shipping cost is calculated based on average shipping cost per unit multiply by total quantity. The total shipping cost of USD 3,849.74 were spent for purchasing this items.

Item	Shipping cost per Unit(USD)	Quantity	Total Shipping cost (USD)
Rain Gauges	62	41	2,542.00
DS18B20 Temperature Sensor	1.34	10	13.40
Wind Direction - PCB Sensor	7.56	24	181.44
Wind Direction - MOD Sensor	23.11	19	439.09
Wind Speed - PCB Sensor	3.05	21	64.05
Wind Speed - MOD Sensor	13.22	19	251.18
OpenLog	1.95	33	64.35
SI1145 UV IR Visible Light Sensor	0.96	49	47.04
BME 280	1.29	87	112.23
HRXL - MaxSonar -WRLST Water Level Sensor	19.28	7	134.96
Total Cost (USD)			3,849.74

Table 13: Shipping cost of the Sensors

5 Total Cost incurred in 4nse system

According to the cost effectiveness of the 4nse system (Table 11,12,13), the total cost spent for developing all 37 Weather station including 16 MOD, 16 PCB & 06 River Gauges as follows;

Type of Station	No of Station	Station Cost (USD)	Total Cost (USD)
4onse MOD	16	737.22	11,795.52
4onse PCB	16	766.37	12,261.92
4onse PCB River Gauge	6	652.16	3,912.96
Total cost of the 4onse 37 Station (USD)			27,970.40

Table 14: Total cost incurred in 4onse system

According to the Table 14, it was spent USD 11,795.52 for 16 MOD station, USD 12,261.92 for 16 PCB station and USD 3,912.96 for 06 River Gauges. Approximately USD 27,970.40 was spent for developed 37 4onse Systems.

Chapter 03 - Introduction

This chapter discussed other Indirect Cost incurred in 4onse Project. It Includes the Installation cost, Maintenance cost, Replacement cost, Communication cost and Travel cost.

1 Installation Cost

For the Installation of the 4onse system base, it was spent in average half a day. And, Table 15 shows the Material cost ratio as cement: sand: Aggregate is 1:3:3. According to the Labor cost and Material Cost, It was spent total LKR 2,950.00 (USD 18.67) for Installation cost. (Consider the Average USD rate as 158 for the installation of July 2018)

Labor Cost	(LKR)	(USD)
Mason	1,000.00	6.33
Helper	750.00	4.75
Total Cost	1,750.00	11.08
Material Cost	(LKR)	(USD)
Cement 25KG	500.00	3.16
Sand	500.00	3.16
Aggregate	200.00	1.27
Total Cost	1,200.00	7.59

Table 15: Installation Cost

2 Monthly Personnel Cost for Maintenance

The monthly personnel cost for maintenance of the system was as follows;

We have two people paid for maintenance the weather stations and total salary is LKR 180,770.00 per month. According to the Table 16, cost per station per month is LKR 4,757.10 (USD 31.71). (Consider the USD rate as 150)

	(LKR)	(USD)
Total Salary per month	180,770	1205.13
No of Stations	38	38
Cost per station per month	4757.10	31.71

Table 16: Monthly personnel Cost for Maintenance

3 Monthly Replacement Cost

Table 17 shows the Replaced Item of weather station and the replacement cost for each item. According to that, the most frequently replaced items are BME 280, Battery, Arduino Mega2560 and PCB Board. The total replacement cost was USD 2,158.52 for the time period of August 2018 to June 2019. And monthly Replacement cost was USD 215.85.

Repalced Sensor/ Item	Reason	Quantity	Cost (USD)
BME280	Frequently Stopped working due to corrosion and show higher value rate	35	446.6
SI1145 UVIR Visible Sensor	Due to BH1750 cannot measure up to 100klx	30	145.2
Solar Panel	Stopped working (Withikuliya and kedapathvehera WS)	4	115.28
Solar Charger	Battery is not charging (Kedapathvehera, Gajanaggegama and Polpithigama WS)	4	80
Battery		19	704.14
OpenLog	Fail to read	4	58.84
Arduino Mega	Not working (all PCB WS)	14	160.58
Temperature Sensor	Not working	3	5.28
Wind Direction sensor	Not Working (Bathalagoda, Gajanaggegama, Hulogedara WS)	6	83.94
Wind Speed Sensor	Not working (Hulogedara WS)	7	88.06
SIMCOM SIM800	Not working (Kumbukgete, SB Herath and Hulogedara WS)	3	27.36
Reset Circuit		3	29.64
PCB Board		12	213.6
Total Replacement Cost			2158.52
Replacement cost per month			215.85

Table 17: Monthly Replacement Cost

4 Monthly Communication Cost

The monthly communication cost per system was approximated as follows;

Usually we used Two service Providers as Dialog and Mobitel for Communication. For Mobitel, It was spent average LKR 299.00 (USD 1.69) for one station and for the Dialog, it was spent average LKR 349.00 (USD 1.98) for one station. So, approximately LKR 11,400.00 () were spent for monthly communication cost for 38 Weather Stations.

5 Monthly Travel cost

Option 01: Using Rented Vehicle

Noramally we were planned to cover 14 Weather station per week. For that, there were two visit per week and it was covered 07 weather station per visit. If we rented a vehicle from Kurunegala town to Field, Monthly Travel cost is approximated as follows;

Assumption 01: Consider the cost/km as LKR 45.00 (*most of the vehicle rentals is charged as LKR 45.00/km*)

Assumption 02: Consider the Average Travel Distance of Field visit as 200km

Assumption 03: USD Rate =170 (considering the average USD rate from August 2018 to June 2019)

Journey (Rented Vehicle)	
From Kurunegala to Field (Km)	200
Cost per Km (LKR)	45.00
Travel Cost (LKR)	9,000.00
Travel cost per week (LKR)	18,000.00
Travel cost per Month (LKR)	72,000.00
Travel cost per Month (USD)	423.53

Table 18: Monthly Travel cost for rented vehicle

According to the Table 18, it was spent LKR 72,000.00 (USD 423.53) for Monthly Travel cost.

Option 02: Using University Vehicle

Noramally we were planned to cover 14 Weather station per week. For that, there were two visit per week and it was covered 07 weather station per visit. If we used University vehicle to Field visits, Monthly Travel cost is approximated as follows;

University Vehicle is the commonly used method for field visits. For one visit, appoximately used 30L of diesel. And also include expressway fee as LKR 500.00 appoximately for the Visit. According to the Table 19, it was spent LKR 35,200.00 (USD 207.06) for Monthly Travel cost. USD Rate =170 (considering the average USD rate from August 2018 to June 2019)

Journey (University Vehicle)	
Fuel for one Visit (L)	30
Fuel (Diesel) Charges per litre (LKR)	130
Total Fuel (Diesel) Charges (LKR)	3,900
Expressway Fee (LKR)	500
Travel Cost per visit (LKR)	4,400
Travel Cost per Week (LKR)	8,800
Travel Cost per Month (LKR)	35,200
Travel Cost per Month (USD)	207.06

Table 19: Monthly Travel cost for University vehicle

Chapter 04 - Introduction

This chapter includes the comparison of cost of 4nse system with other automatic weather station in the International market.

1 Comparison of costs and accuracy levels of 4nse system and other automatic weather stations in the market

The 4nse system was compared with some wireless and automatic weather station in the market which measure similar parameters (Table 20). The rationale for select these Wireless and Automatic WS is having the similar parameters we used in 4nse WS. Although there are varying accuracy levels of the parameters measured by each system, the 4nse is capable of measuring nine parameters with a relative low cost.

Measured Parameters & other available features	4onse MOD Prototype		4onse PCB Prototype		Vantage Pro Plus Station		MetPak RG Weather Station		Rainwise PORTLOG 805-1018 Poratable WS	
	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy
Rainfall	√	0.2mm	√	0.2mm	√	0.2mm	√	0.2mm	√	±2% @1.0 inches/hr
Wind Speed	√	0.6m/s	√	0.2-0.4m/s	√	12m/s	√	12m/s	√	±2% of full scale
Wind Direction	√	10%	√	±3°	√	±3°	√	±3°	√	±3°
Temperature	√	±0.5°C	√	±5°C	√	±0.1°C	√	±0.1°C	√	±.25°C
Relative Humidity	√	±3%	√	±3%	√	±0.8%	√	±0.8%	√	2%
Barometric Pressure	√	±1hPa	√	±1hPa	√	±0.5hPa	√	±0.5hPa	√	±0.5hPa
Light Intensity/Solar Radiation	√	1.44 times sensor out/Actual lx	√	1.44 times sensor out/Actual lx	-	-	-	-	√	Max ±5% Typical ±3%
Soil Moisture	-	-	√	±2%	-	-	-	-	-	-
River Gauge	-	-	√	±0.5cm	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wireless Communication	√		√		√		√		√	
Cost (without shipping)		624.81		1304.63*		1490		2200.94		4546
Cost (with shipping)		877.78		1874.14*		1665.02		2734.19		5036

* Cost Include with River Gauge USD 623

Table 20: Comparison table of costs and accuracy levels of 4onse system and other automatic weather stations in the market

Reference

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